

THE FUTURE OF ENGLISH

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ANNOTATION: The language has developed into a leading international lingua franca used by millions of speakers in different linguistic and cultural contexts worldwide. This paper examines an applied linguistic conceptual interest concerning the future of English and its varieties in light of its current status, the challenges it experiences, and the conspicuous threats to half of the world's languages.

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Nowadays, the world is developing . In the world many people communicate English language because it is get a second language in a world. In addition, 2 billion of people speak this language .

English, as any other language, is a living and dynamic system, and it transforms according to the way its speakers use it. For this reason, today's English will be very different in about a century. Ben Bowlin, the author of the blog HowStuffWorks, consults this question in a very informative video.

Then, did you know that English native speakers are among the minority of the world's population of English speakers? Perhaps even more astonishing is that today's largest English speaking country is in fact China.

According to Bowlin, the course the English language will take is very dependent on people speaking it as a second language. To consider this, you might want to think about how English has evolved in different countries. The differences between American English and British English, and perhaps even Australian or Indian English, highlights how diverted both its dialects and words have gotten.

Indeed, as we are moving toward a trend of people using English as their second language, we will see that English language will continue to develop in a similar manner as before, but new dialects, slang, words and perhaps even linguistic variations will evolveⁱ

It is the language of science, aviation, computers, diplomacy and tourism. Last but

not least, it is the language of international communication, the media and the internet. Whether it is for professional or personal reasons, understanding the importance of English will help you reach your goals.

Nowadays, many films, TV shows, books and music are published and produced in English. By understanding English, you won't need to rely on translations and subtitles anymore. By accessing these media, you will also continuously improve your English listening and reading skills.

English is currently the language of the internet. An estimated of 565 million people use the internet every day and about 52% of the world's most visited websites are displayed in English. Therefore, learning this language gives access to over half the content of the internet, which might not be available otherwise. Whether it is for fun or for work, if you understand English, you will be able to exchange information with more people online and use many more materials.ⁱⁱ

Why is it important to speak English ?

Speaking English allows you to actually broaden your world, from job opportunities to the ability to relate to people from every country.

Knowing the language makes it much more interesting every trip.

Anywhere you want to go in the world you can find someone who speaks English. If we account only the country where the English language is the official language, the United Kingdom, Australia, U.S.A., Canada, Ireland, New Zealand and the Caribbean countries, there are more than 400 million native English speakers.

Simply put, we must recognize that English is an international language, the main language of this planet.

The statistics reveal that more than a quarter of the world's population speaks English that means that about 1.6 billion people understand and relate with the help of the language of Shakespeare. To not mention that most of the films are in English, the largest film industry, Hollywood, is produced in English.

It is true that in the world are more than 3 billion people who speak Chinese, however it is very unlikely that in addition to the mother tongue there is someone else who wants to learn Chinese characters.

Most of the international trade agreements are concluded in English and is the most

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widely used language for international business meetings.

Good English is not only classy but a possibility to continue studies and specializations in the best universities in the world, which are in fact, in countries where they speak English.

Education is very important to improve yourself but learning English also improves the quality of life. You have access to jobs that you could not even take into consideration, you can evaluate an international career and you can live in many countries with the ease of being able to go shopping or negotiate rent for the house.

The benefits they bring in the life of a person's knowledge of the English language are countless. What is important to understand is that the English language is able to knock down a lot of barriers, including cultural ones.

Knowing the habits and customs of other countries allows us to understand ourselves and others. By better understanding our fellow man around the world we are always surprised at how we are different and similar at the same time.

The English language allows us to relate and therefore to understand each other.ⁱⁱⁱ

Reference

ⁱ <https://termcoord.eu/2020/04/future-english-language/>

ⁱⁱ <https://www.etsglobal.org/pl/en/blog/news/importance-of-learning-english>

ⁱⁱⁱ <https://www.universitylanguageschool.com/student-blog-why-is-it-important-to-speak-english/>